

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

Deliverable 2.3

Deliverable Number	D2.3
Deliverable Title	OSTrails Software and Services V2
Version n°	V1.0
Status	Final
Type	Other
Dissemination Level	Public
Work Package	WP2
Lead Beneficiary	CITE
Delivery Date	31/01/2026
Author(s)	Georgios Kakalettris (CITE), Diamantis Tziotzios (CITE), John Shepherdson (CESSDA), Katja Moilanen (TAU-FSD/CESSDA), Matti Heinonen (TAU-FSD/CESSDA), Oana Dragomir (SOCIB), Miguel Charcos-Llorens (SOCIB), Menzo Windhouwer (KNAW HuC), Renaud Duyme (PaNOSC/ESRF), Mike Priddy (KNAW DANS), Wilko Steinhoff (KNAW DANS), Paolo Manghi (OpenAIRE), Leonidas Pispiringas (OpenAIRE), Katerina Iatropoulou (OpenAIRE), Mark Wilkinson (UPM), Daniel Garijo (UPM),

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe framework programme under grant agreement No. 101130187. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

	Pablo Alarcón (UPM), Claudio Atzori (CNR), Jakub Jirka (CODE), Tomasz Miksa (TUW), Filip Kovacevic (TUW), Suvini Lai (TUW), Susanna-Assunta Sansone (UOXF), Allyson Lister (UOXF), Milo Thursthon (UOXF), Matej Ďurčo (OEAW/ACDH), Vera Maria Charvát (OEAW/ACDH)
Editor(s)	Georgios Kakalettris (CITE), Diamantis Tziotzios (CITE)
Reviewers	Baptiste Cecconi (OBSPM), Jens Harald Aasheim (SIKT)
Approved by	Natalia Manola (OpenAIRE)

Revision History

VERSION	STATUS	DATE	DESCRIPTION	AUTHORS
0.0	Draft	4/11/2025	Initial document structure & content from previous version	Georgios Kakalettris (CITE), Diamantis Tziotzios (CITE)
0.1	Draft	5/11/2025	Edited sections for service/software progress reporting on M14-M24, incl plans for M32	(Author's list)
0.5	Draft	3/12/2025	Content collection completed	(Author's list)
0.6	Draft	19/12/2025	Edited for review after dross-checking information with authors	Georgios Kakalettris (CITE), Diamantis Tziotzios (CITE)
0.9	Review	26/01/2026	Comments addressed	Baptiste Cecconi (OBSPM), Jens Harald Aasheim (SIKT)
1.0	Final	30/1/2026	Edited and prepared for quality assurance	Elli Papadopoulou (ARC); Maria Kontopidi (ARC)

Author List

ORGANISATION	NAME	CONTACT INFORMATION
CITE	Georgios Kakalettris, Diamantis Tziotzios	g.kakalettris@cite.gr dtziotzios@cite.gr
CESSDA	John Shepherdson	john.shepherdson@cessda.eu
TAU-FSD/CESSDA	Katja Moilanen, Matti Heinonen	katja.moilanen@tuni.fi matti.heinonen@tuni.fi
SOCIB	Oana Dragomir, Miguel Charcos-Llorens	odragomir@socib.es mcharcos@socib.es
KNAW HuC	Menzo Windhouwer	menzo.windhouwer@di.huc.knaw.nl
PaNOSC/ESRF	Renaud Duyme	renaud.duyme@esrf.fr

KNAW DANS	Mike Priddy, Wilko Steinhoff	mike.priddy@dans.knaw.nl wilko.steinhoff@dans.knaw.nl
OpenAIRE	Paolo Manghi, Leonidas Pispiringas, Katerina Iatropoulou	paolo.manghi@openaire.eu leonidas.pispiringas@openaire.eu kiatrop@athenarc.gr
UPM	Mark Wilkinson, Daniel Garijo, Pablo Alarcón	mark.wilkinson@upm.es daniel.garijo@upm.es pablo.alarcon@upm.es
CNR	Claudio Atzori	claudio.atzori@isti.cnr.it
CODE	Jakub Jirka	jakub.jirka@codevence.com
TUW	Tomasz Miksa, Filip Kovacevic, Suvini Lai	tomasz.miksa@tuwien.ac.at filip.kovacevic@tuwien.ac.at ka.lai@tuwien.ac.at
UOXF	Susanna-Assunta Sansone, Allyson Lister, Milo Thursthon	susanna-assunta.sansone@oerc.ox.ac.uk allyson.lister@oerc.ox.ac.uk milo.thurston@oerc.ox.ac.uk
OEAW/ACDH	Matej Ďurčo, Vera Maria Charvát	matej.durco@oeaw.ac.at veramaria.charvat@oeaw.ac.at

Table of Contents

Disclaimer	7
Abbreviations List.....	8
Executive Summary.....	10
1. Introduction	11
1.1. Context	11
1.2. Deliverable Description	11
1.3. Structure of Document.....	12
2. DMP Platforms	13
2.1. ARGOS/OpenCDMP	13
2.2. DAMAP	14
2.3. Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW).....	16
3. SKG Platforms	18
3.1. CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC).....	18
3.2. FAIRsharing.....	21
3.3. International Virtual Observatory Alliance Registry (IVOA Registry).....	22
3.4. Joint European Research Infrastructure of Coastal Observatories - Coastal Ocean Resource Environment (JERICO-CORE).....	23
3.5. OpenAIRE Graph	25
3.6. European Synchrotron Radiation Facility Data Portal (ESRF-DP).....	27
3.7. SOCIB KG	29
3.8. SSH Open Marketplace (SSHOMP)	30
3.9. Virtual Language Observatory (VLO).....	31
3.10. OPUS CTA Provenance.....	32
4. FAIR Assessment Platforms	35
4.1. CESSDA Metadata Validator (CMV).....	35
4.2. FAIR-Aware	37
4.3. FAIR Champion (ex FAIR Evaluator)	38
4.4. FAIR Assessment Authoring Tool.....	40
4.5. FAIR Validator	41

4.6.	FAIR Research Objects Assessment (FAIROS)	43
4.7.	Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR (FOOPSI).....	44
4.8.	IVOA Services Validation.....	46
4.9.	PADC Validator	47
5.	Other Supporting Services and Platforms	49
5.1.	CESSDA ELSST.....	49
5.2.	CESSDA Vocabulary Service	50
5.3.	CESSDA Metadata Aggregator	52
5.4.	FAIRassist.....	54
5.5.	Lenticular Lens	55
5.6.	OpenAIRE Broker	56
5.7.	OpenOrgs	58
5.8.	ROHub.....	60
5.9.	SOMEF.....	62
5.10.	SSH Data Citation Service	63
5.11.	SSH Vocabulary Commons	65
5.12.	DataRepositóriUM.....	66
5.13.	RCAAP.....	68
6.	Conclusions – Next Steps	70
7.	References	73
	Annex I – Description Template	74
	Software/Service XYX.....	74

List of Figures

Figure 1: Overview of tool status.....	71
Figure 2: Tools implementing refinements in OSTrails WP2, per category	71
Figure 3: Tools reporting refinements to date in D2.3	72

Disclaimer

This document contains description of the OSTrails project findings, work, and products. Its content is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY-4.0) license¹.

In case you believe that this document harms in any way IPR held by you as a person or as a representative of an entity, please do notify us immediately.

The authors of this document have taken any available measure to ensure that its content is accurate, consistent, and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document hold any sort of responsibility that might occur as a result of using its content.

The publication herein was produced in the framework of the EU-funded OSTrails project (Grant Agreement No 101130187). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the OSTrails consortium and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency.

**Funded by
the European Union**

¹ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>

Abbreviations List

API	Application Programming Interface
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment
CRIS	Current Research Information System
DC	Dublin Core
DCMI Metadata Terms	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative Metadata Terms (often mentioned as dcterms by the commonly used namespace)
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EUPL	European Public License
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FOSS	Free Open-Source Software
FTR	(FTR)
IF	Interoperability Framework
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JSON for Linked Data
maDMP	Machine Actionable Data Management Plan
OAI	Open Archives Initiative
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OID	Object Identifier
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PID	Persistent Identifier
PMH	Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
RO	Research Object
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language

TBD	To be delivered / To be discussed (depending on context)
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UI	User Interface
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URN	Uniform Resource Name
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

This report accompanies D2.3 “OSTrails Software and Services V2” which refers to the second release of the software produced by WP2 as a result of alignment with the objectives of the project and the expectations, directives and requirements stemming from the work of WP1 and WP2 and the Description of Work of the project.

The report presents results from the work performed on requirements originating from (a) the OSTrails Interoperability Framework requirements, (b) the alignment with indicated common technologies and standards, (c) the filling of the gaps identified in technologies at hand during previous period and (d) the targets set in the Description of Work of OSTrails.

This report presents a self-contained comprehensive listing of this software, its status and how to access it - as a service, source code, documentation, executable or in any other form foreseen for each platform - a summary of the work performed in the preceding period to align with OSTrails requirements. Each software platform also reports forthcoming work in OSTrails to further align with the requirements.

Most of the software addressed by D2.3 work predates the OSTrails project and is organised in four categories: (a) DMP Platforms, (b) SKG Platforms, (c) FAIR Assessment Platforms and (d) Other Supporting Services and Platforms, as established in work preceding [D2.2](#) delivery.

In total 35 tools are listed in the aforementioned manner, out of which 3 DMP tools, 10 SKG Platforms, 9 FAIR Assessment Platforms and 13 supporting services and platforms. Out of those, almost 90% have already implemented some form of alignment in OSTrails, while the rest have plans to implement integrations or adaptations in the remaining WP2 formal software releases. Most of those tools are free and open-source code software.

The final release (D2.4, M32) will consolidate these integrations and deliver enhanced interoperability across the Plan-Track-Assess pathway, including tighter DMP-SKG linkages, expanded FAIR assessment coverage, and validated end-to-end workflows informed by WP3 and WP4 pilot feedback.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

Deliverable D2.3 is product of work performed in Work Package 2, “Plan-Track-Assess Alignment Implementation”, of OSTrails project, across all of its 4 tasks, that is Data Management Plan (DMP) Platforms (T2.1), Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG) Platforms (T2.2), FAIR² Assessment Platforms (T2.3) and Supporting Services and Resources (T2.4) alignment.

It is the second of three versions OSTrails Software and Services, increasing alignment, the first one delivered on M14 and the last one to be delivered on M32 of the project.

1.2. Deliverable Description

Deliverable 2.3 is the software and services evolving in OSTrails and as such can be found in respective source code and binaries repositories or service endpoints.

This report describes the second release of the software and services delivered by Work Package 2 tasks. Those tasks focus on aligning existing software platforms and tools with the project objectives outlined in the Description of Work, as well as the expectations, directives and requirements emanating from work carried out so far by both Work Package 1 and Work Package 2. These fall into the following categories:

- Requirements coming from Interoperability framework.
- Expectations regarding the adoption of core technologies and standards identified as suitable and mature for adoption across tools.
- Directives for gaps that need to be filled in.
- Specific work targets introduced at Description of Work.

Those have been enumerated in Section 2, “Requirements”, of [D2.2](#).

The software dealt with in WP2 is organised in four categories:

- (a) DMP Platforms,
- (b) SKG Platforms,
- (c) FAIR Assessment Platforms and
- (d) Other Supporting Services and Platforms

Those were established in [D2.1](#) entitled “.1: Analysis of the OSTrails Interoperability Framework Tools Compliance” and presented in the report preceding D2.3, i.e. the [D2.2](#).

As the software predates the OSTrails project, the deliverable refers to enhancements and extensions of existing software, rather than new platforms and tools. However not

² FAIR refers to principles for Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets emphasizing on machine-actionability allowing researchers, scientists, and other human stakeholders to deal with data of rapidly increasing volume, complexity, and creation speed.

all software analysed in the context of WP2 and presented in [D2.1](#) is evolving in WP2, thus specific platforms / tools are not included in this report.

As mentioned, this report accompanies software delivery as a supporting document and is not itself the deliverable per se. It aims to provide the reader with a self-contained, comprehensive summary of the work performed up to this software release and shape the direction of forthcoming work, a schema for the homogeneous description of the software implemented has been shaped and utilised across the document.

Following this approach, the main part of this report consists of information provided for each software component that has evolved in this period, along the lines presented earlier, referring to:

- Identification of the software, containing the formal name of the service / platform / tool, the category the software falls into, and its Technology Readiness Level, along any identifier or version number applicable to it.
- References for accessing the platform/service and/or its source code, if Open Source, and its documentation along with any relevant information about how it is being offered to its users/audience.
- Licensing and ownership information.
- Reference to software Quality Assurance measures taken in delivery of the software.
- Brief presentation of the work performed in OSTrails from M15 up to M24, in alignment with its objectives.
- Plan for the work to be performed in alignment with the main project's milestones.

1.3. Structure of Document

The rest of the document is structured as follows.

- In [section 2](#) the work performed in each software component, that falls under the category of "DMP platform" is presented.
- In [section 3](#) and under a similar fashion with the previous section, the SKG Platforms work performed is presented.
- In [section 4](#), in a similar way the FAIR Assessment Platforms are listed.
- In [section 5](#), work on all remaining software supporting the three aforementioned categories of platforms, is presented.
- Finally, in [section 6](#), overall conclusions on the progress of work and key points of next steps of implementation are presented.

2. DMP Platforms

Here we describe DMP platforms software / services.

2.1. ARGOS/OpenCDMP

Name	ARGOS (Service) / OpenCDMP (Software)		
Category	DMP		
Service URL	https://argos.openaire.eu/		
Version	2.1.0	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	CITE, OpenAIRE	Contributors	ARC
License	Code: EUPL1.2 (https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/licence/european-union-public-licence-version-12-eupl) Documentation: CC By 4.0 (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)		
Forms of availability	Source code and Docker Container Images		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/OpenCDMP/OpenCDMP		
Documentation URL	https://opencdmp.github.io/ https://argos.openaire.eu/user-guide		
Other repositories	Source code: https://github.com/OpenCDMP/OpenCDMP Container Images: https://hub.docker.com/u/opencdmp Maven: https://mvnrepository.com/artifact/org.opencdmp		
PID	Not available		
Software Quality Assurance measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CI/CD infrastructure to ensure repeatable, trusted delivery. - Static Code Analysis using SonarQube software. - OWASP Top 10 compliance. - Use of industry standard AuthN/AuthZ solutions and practices. 		

<p>Work performed</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extended the External Reference model to support additional integration options based on pilot needs. - Completed the design and implementation of the internal structures enabling the tool to call the DMP Evaluation Service and store and present its results. - Completed the current-stage integration with the DMP Evaluation Service. - Implemented updates for the maDMP Common API, enabling the system to handle changes received through this API and manage their impact on internal workflows. - Initiated the implementation of an independent, standalone service providing the maDMP Common API: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Tool-agnostic service maintaining its own persistency layer that stores and serves maDMPs, and integrates with the main tool via a message queue. o Implements the fetch endpoints of the maDMP Common API. - Worked on repository and CRIS system integrations for pilots. - Implemented an example integration with selected endpoints of the SKG-IF. - Extended documentation to cover new improvements and extensions. 				
<p>Milestones</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="448 1133 647 1173">Month</th> <th data-bbox="647 1133 1374 1173">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="448 1173 647 1617"> <p>32</p> </td> <td data-bbox="647 1173 1374 1617"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finalize the integration of the DMP/FAIR Evaluation Service. - Adopt the OSTrails Application Profile. - Address additional pilot requirements, based on prioritization of incoming requests. - Finalize project documentation according to project requirements. - Continue improving previously delivered features and follow new technical directions defined by the project. </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	<p>32</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finalize the integration of the DMP/FAIR Evaluation Service. - Adopt the OSTrails Application Profile. - Address additional pilot requirements, based on prioritization of incoming requests. - Finalize project documentation according to project requirements. - Continue improving previously delivered features and follow new technical directions defined by the project.
Month	Description				
<p>32</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finalize the integration of the DMP/FAIR Evaluation Service. - Adopt the OSTrails Application Profile. - Address additional pilot requirements, based on prioritization of incoming requests. - Finalize project documentation according to project requirements. - Continue improving previously delivered features and follow new technical directions defined by the project. 				

2.2. DAMAP

<p>Name</p>	<p>DAMAP, a tool for machine actionable DMPs</p>
<p>Category</p>	<p>DMP</p>

Service URL	https://damap.it.tuwien.ac.at/		
Version	V 4.6.1	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	Technische Universität Wien / Technische Universität Graz	Contributors	Technische Universität Wien Technische Universität Graz
License	MIT License (https://opensource.org/license/mit)		
Forms of availability	Code repository		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/tuwien-csd/damap-frontend https://github.com/tuwien-csd/damap-backend		
Documentation URL	https://damap.org/		
Other repositories	None		
PID	Not Available		
Software Quality Assurance measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unit Tests - Static Code Analysis 		
Work performed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exhaustive code analysis of DAMAPs internal data model to avoid potential problems when integrating with the new common API. - Implementation of the first basic API schema draft in DAMAP as a proof of concept. - Experimentation with code generators to ensure that new revisions of API or the common standard can easily be added to DAMAP. - Implementation of a strict API mode in DAMAP, where the API will reject DMPs that could lead to data loss in the system. 		

Milestones	Month	Description
	32	Integrate with DMP Evaluation Service Replace the OpenAIRE API with for the SKG API Replace the custom Invenio Integration with one using the common API

2.3. Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW)

Name	FAIR Wizard (Service) / Data Stewardship Wizard (Software)		
Category	DMP		
Service URL	https://fair-wizard.com/ , https://ds-wizard.org		
Version	4.24	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	Codevence	Contributors	
License	Apache License 2.0 http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0		
Forms of availability	Source code and Docker Container Images, SaaS		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/ds-wizard https://github.com/ds-wizard/engine-frontend https://github.com/ds-wizard/engine-backend https://github.com/ds-wizard/engine-tools		
Documentation URL	https://guide.ds-wizard.org/en/latest/		
Other repositories	https://github.com/ds-wizard/dsw-deployment-example		
PID	Not available		

<p>Software Quality Assurance measures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing with industry best practices (https://www.bestpractices.dev/en/projects/4975) - CI/CD Infrastructure - End-to-end tests, unit tests frontend and backend - QA process 				
<p>Work performed</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continued development of Knowledge Models maDMP workflows, focusing on standardization and user interface improvements to meet RDA DMP Common Standard requirements. - Refined knowledge management structures for compatibility with IF specifications and RDA DMP Common Standard. - Developed preliminary API adapter prototypes to support interoperability with IF ecosystem while keeping the internal data structures and flexibility. - Aligned feature priorities based on gathered use case requirements from pilot projects, ensuring responsiveness to diverse community needs. - Preliminary design for inclusion of DMP evaluation services following the current specification from T3.3 - Running OSTrails FAIR Assessment Authoring Tool and content development support 				
<p>Milestones</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="448 1263 647 1308">Month</th> <th data-bbox="647 1263 1374 1308">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="448 1308 647 1507">32</td> <td data-bbox="647 1308 1374 1507">Integration of DMP Evaluation service integration, integration with FAIR evaluation services and other services as identified as need in pilots. Updated API adapter and mappings according to latest OSTrails AP.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	Integration of DMP Evaluation service integration, integration with FAIR evaluation services and other services as identified as need in pilots. Updated API adapter and mappings according to latest OSTrails AP.
Month	Description				
32	Integration of DMP Evaluation service integration, integration with FAIR evaluation services and other services as identified as need in pilots. Updated API adapter and mappings according to latest OSTrails AP.				

3. SKG Platforms

3.1. CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC)

Name	CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) - ID002		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/		
Version	4.1.1 ³	TRL	8 ⁴
Copyright owner(s)	CESSDA ERIC	Contributors	CESSDA and Service Providers, DoraVentures, Fox Online Solutions, Open Concept
License	Software: Apache-2.0 https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0 Documentation: CC-BY-4.0 https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/		
Forms of availability	Code repository, source code bundle, service endpoint, app marketplace		
Code repository URL	Application: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.searchkit.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.metadata.harvester.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.userguide.git OAI-PMH endpoint: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.doc-store.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.client.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.oai-pmh-repo-handler.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.oai-pmh-repo-handler.git 		

³ Released 5 NOV 2025

⁴ <https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/services/requirements.html>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.devguide.git <p>SKG-IF:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.skg-if.api.git
Documentation URL	<p>User Guide: https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/documentation/</p> <p>Search API: https://api.tech.cessda.eu/ (select 'CESSDA DC Search API v2')</p> <p>OAI-PMH API: https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=Identify</p> <p>OAI-PMH Developer's guide: Developer Documentation — CESSDA Metadata Aggregator 0.2.0 documentation</p>
Other repositories	<p>Zenodo (Application):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3786299 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3786355 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5711127 <p>Zenodo (OAI-PMH endpoint):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779957 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779936 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779782 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779897 <p>Zenodo (SKG-IF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17572658 <p>EOSC EU Node Marketplace:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/datasources/21.11166%252Fu6za4c <p>SSH Open Marketplace:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/etR4oA
PID	<p>Application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3786299 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3786355 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5711127

	<p>OAI-PMH endpoint:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779957 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779936 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779782 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779897 <p>SKG-IF:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17572658
<p>Software Quality Assurance measures</p>	<p>The source code for CESSDA Service components is periodically evaluated against the CESSDA Software Maturity Levels (https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/sml/index.html). Example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md <p>The Jenkins build fails if the CESSDA Software Quality Gate is not achieved (https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/software/quality-gate.html)</p> <p>The repositories are checked using the EOSC SQAaaS tool (https://sqaaaS.eosc-synergy.eu/full-assessment) and README files badged accordingly. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/README.md - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.console/blob/main/README.md <p>Tooling</p> <p>Jenkins: https://jenkins.cessda.eu/ (includes Unit Tests, test coverage, Static Analysis)</p> <p>SonarQube: https://sonarqube.cessda.eu/projects (assesses Reliability, Security, Maintainability)</p> <p>JMeter: https://jmeter.apache.org/ (load testing)</p>
<p>Work performed</p>	<p>Mapping between CESSDA data catalogue metadata and RDA SKG IF model & SKG IF OpenAPI Product schema, and feedback provided on the SKG-IF.</p> <p>Agreement has been reached on modifications needed to CESSDA's DDI-C and DDI-L profiles to incorporate RORs. Namely, add PIDs for the organizational creators (author, PI) and for the affiliation of the individual creators.</p>

	<p>Modifications adopted by some Publishers to enrich their metadata, which is now in the CESSDA Data Catalogue.</p> <p>The initial version of the SKG-IF for the CESSDA Data Catalogue has been released, and feedback provided on the API specification.</p>				
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.
Month	Description				
32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.				

3.2. FAIRsharing

Name	FAIRsharing		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	https://fairsharing.org , https://api.fairsharing.org		
Version	N/A	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	University of Oxford	Contributors	Several ⁵
License	Content: CC-BY-SA-4.0, https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/legalcode		
Forms of availability	Service endpoint, data catalogue		
Code repository URL	<p>Web application: https://github.com/FAIRsharing/fairsharing.github.io/</p> <p>There's also a private API repository.</p>		
Documentation URL	https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing		
Other repositories	https://github.com/FAIRsharing/FAIRsharing-Assistant		

⁵ https://fairsharing.org/community_champions/our_champions

PID	N/A						
Software Quality Assurance measures	CI unit testing, code coverage measurement, njsscan, codacy scanning, brakeman testing on API, API integration testing.						
Work performed	<p>Contributed to the SKG-IF architecture and enriched the FAIRsharing content and graph by working with clusters' champions, to meet their needs as well as the requirements of the DMPs and the FAIR tools. For the DMP side, the integration with DSW is completed, while it is partial with ARGOS and planned with DAMAP.</p> <p>Contributed to the definition of the FAIR assessment IF of Dimensions, Metrics, Benchmarks and Tests. Designed and implemented the new FAIRassist registry component of FAIRsharing, to assist with the assessment. This new registry and (and knowledge graph) will describe FAIR Principles (or Dimensions), related Metrics and Benchmarks (that will be related to relevant standards, in the main FAIRsharing registry), the latter two cross-referenced to the Tests.</p>						
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Production system</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	32	Production system
Month	Description						
32	Production system						

3.3. International Virtual Observatory Alliance Registry (IVOA Registry)

Name	IVOA Registry		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	http://rofr.ivoa.net/ https://registry.euro-vo.org/evor/#home (GUI) http://dc.g-vo.org/browse/rr/q (RegTAP protocol) http://voparis-rr.obspm.fr/browse/rr/q (RegTAP protocol)		
Version	N/A	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	IVOA	Contributors	All data providers (many, worldwide)

License	Not specified				
Forms of availability	Service endpoint using IVOA RegTAP protocol				
Code repository URL	Several implementations, relying on several frameworks.				
Documentation URL	For data providers: https://wiki.ivoa.net/twiki/bin/view/IVOA/GettingIntoTheRegistry For users: https://wiki.ivoa.net/twiki/bin/view/IVOA/lvoaResReg#How%20do%20I%20use%20it?				
Other repositories	N/A				
PID	No PID for software.				
Software Quality Assurance measures	Each framework has its own implementation. However, the interfaces must pass validation tests (see IVOA Validator tools)				
Work performed	The mapping between the IVOA registry resource and the SKG IF has been defined. The prototype SKG-IF interface is being developed. We proposed a new entity for connecting data resources to interfaces serving the dataset.				
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>SKG-IF interface on IVOA Registry at ObsParis</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	SKG-IF interface on IVOA Registry at ObsParis
Month	Description				
32	SKG-IF interface on IVOA Registry at ObsParis				

3.4. Joint European Research Infrastructure of Coastal Observatories - Coastal Ocean Resource Environment (JERICO-CORE)

Name	JERICO Coastal Ocean Resource Environment (JERICO-CORE)
Category	SKG / Supporting Service and Platform

Service URL	https://ui.core.jerico-ri.eu and https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu (deprovisioned at end of JERICO-S3 project) https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/jerico_core/home (Blue Cloud VRE will host OSTrails interoperable SKG/DMP/FAIR assessment services)		
Version	0.2.9	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	JERICO	Contributors	IEEE, SOCIB, MARIS, IFREMER, AZTI, ETT, BLIT, IODE, CNRS-LOV, CNR, FMI, TALTECH, SYKE, EPOS, RBINS, SMHI
License	All Rights Reserved		
Forms of availability	Gitlab repository, docker container registry.		
Code repository URL	SDK https://gitlab.priv.socib.es/data-center/ejerico_harvester API (https://pypi.org/project/ejerico-harvester/ is the public substitute) https://giltab.priv.socib.es/jerico/core_endpoint https://gitlab.priv.socib.es/jerico/core_endpoint/container_registry		
Documentation URL	https://api.core.jerico-ri.eu/api/swagger (deprovisioned at end of JERICO-S3 project)		
Other repositories	https://github.com/socib/jerico-core.metadata https://pypi.org/project/ejerico-harvester		
PID	Not available		
Software Quality Assurance measures	Static code analysis, accessibility compliance testing.		
Work performed	The work performed to date addresses the following requirements: DMP-R1, DMP-R3, SKG.R3, IF-R1, IF-R3, IF-R5. They are the following:		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data model evaluation and re-design to comply with RDA standards. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o SKG-IF core data model was implemented; to extend instrument representation - Storage re-design to facilitate assessments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o maDMPs are stored in the SKG; assessments dashboard to be implemented - Integration of DMP in SKG <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Import of maDMP and representation in the graph is in progress - DMP editor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o RDA DCS data model implemented; JSON export in progress - Harvesters' agent integration into DMP editor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Development in progress <p>JERICO-SKG and SOCIB SKG will be two instances of the same service: the former to serve the wider marine community and the latter for institutional purpose.</p>				
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Connect with the OpenAIRE Graph to retrieve publication records and enrich the thematic SKG. Deploy the tools in the JERICO Virtual Research Environment/BlueCloud Virtual Lab.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	Connect with the OpenAIRE Graph to retrieve publication records and enrich the thematic SKG. Deploy the tools in the JERICO Virtual Research Environment/BlueCloud Virtual Lab.
Month	Description				
32	Connect with the OpenAIRE Graph to retrieve publication records and enrich the thematic SKG. Deploy the tools in the JERICO Virtual Research Environment/BlueCloud Virtual Lab.				

3.5. OpenAIRE Graph

Name	OpenAIRE Graph		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	https://graph.openaire.eu/		
Version	10.6.0 ⁶	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	OpenAIRE	Contributors	OpenAIRE, ARC, CNR, University of Athens, University of Minho, University of Bielefeld, University of Warsaw,

⁶ OpenAIRE Graph Changelog:
https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/changelog/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

			National Documentation Centre - Greece ⁷⁸
License	CC-BY Overview OpenAIRE Graph Documentation - https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/		
Forms of availability	Service endpoint, data dumps, APIs		
Code repository URL	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/openaire-graph-docs		
Documentation URL	https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/		
Other repositories	Zenodo for data dumps		
PID	DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7488618		
Software Quality Assurance measures	Regular updates, community feedback integration, adherence to open standards		
Work performed	A metadata crosswalk from the OpenAIRE Graph data model and schema to the SKG-IF schema has been implemented, together with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A workflow for the generation of a SKG-IF dump of the OpenAIRE Graph - APIs following the SKG-IF API specification to expose research product metadata - The implementation of SKG-IF API to query other Graph entities is ongoing 		
Milestones	Month	Description	
	32	PROD release of SKG-IF APIs	

⁷ OpenAIRE Graph - The Team: <https://graph.openaire.eu/team>

⁸ The OpenAIRE Research Graph Data Model: https://zenodo.org/records/2643199?utm_source=chatgpt.com

3.6. European Synchrotron Radiation Facility Data Portal (ESRF-DP)

Name	European Synchrotron Radiation Facility Data Portal		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	https://data.esrf.fr		
Version	N/A	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	European Synchrotron Radiation Facility	Contributors	none
License	- MIT License		
Forms of availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ESRF Data Portal : Web site: https://data.esrf.fr - ESRF Data Portal API service: https://icatplus.esrf.fr/ - PaNET/ESRFET integration API : https://esrf-ontologies.readthedocs.io/ - PUMA : https://gitlab.esrf.fr/puma-public/ 		
Code repository URL	- https://gitlab.esrf.fr/icat/data-portal		
Documentation URL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://icat.gitlab-pages.esrf.fr/data-portal/ - https://icat.gitlab-pages.esrf.fr/icat-plus/ - https://icatplus.esrf.fr/api-docs/#/ 		
Other repositories	- https://gitlab.esrf.fr/icat/drac		
PID	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.0e42aa		
Software Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Automated Testing: unit, integration, and end-to-end tests - CI/CD: use pipelines to run tests, build the application and deployment 		

Assurance measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code reviews 				
Work performed	<p>ESRF Data Portal, stores metadata about datasets generated at ESRF facility. Metadata is also exported to Datacite when minting DOI for these datasets.</p> <p>Work performed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SKG-R4: In ESRF Data Portal code. improve dataset metadata sent to Datacite (grant, subject/topic, affiliations) - SKG-R4: In ESRF Data Portal. improve ESRF dataset metadata with PaNET/ESRFET techniques (observations techniques used by ESRF and PaNOSC facilities instruments to generate data). - SKG-R4: Beta deployment of PUMA application (SKG) for a new PaNOSC Facility (SOLEIL synchrotron) to expose publication and grant metadata. - SKG-R2: Delivery of the SKG-IF OpenAPI : https://skg-if.github.io/api/ with the RDA SKG-IF WG. - DMP-R4: Specifications of DMP SKG integration. To allow selection of SKG-IF entities (publication, dataset, software etc...) within DMP editor tools. - FAIR-R6: Definition of community metrics and tests for ESRF datasets FAIR assessment using the FTR specifications and FAIRsharing service. 				
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="446 1223 646 1272">Month</th> <th data-bbox="646 1223 1374 1272">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="446 1272 646 1953">32</td> <td data-bbox="646 1272 1374 1953"> <p>SKG-R1 Implement SKG-IF API on PUMA (ESRF internal SKG) to expose dataset/publication citation links in common format Implement SKG-IF API on ESRF Data Portal to expose datasets in common format</p> <p>SKG-R4 In ESRF Data Portal. improve dataset metadata. add dataset/publication citation links. (source used PUMA SKG-IF API)</p> <p>SKG-R4 Prod deployment of PUMA at SOLEIL facility Update PUMA versions at ESRF and ILL PaNOSC facilities.</p> <p>FAIR-R6 Finalize and run a full benchmark for ESRF datasets.</p> </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	<p>SKG-R1 Implement SKG-IF API on PUMA (ESRF internal SKG) to expose dataset/publication citation links in common format Implement SKG-IF API on ESRF Data Portal to expose datasets in common format</p> <p>SKG-R4 In ESRF Data Portal. improve dataset metadata. add dataset/publication citation links. (source used PUMA SKG-IF API)</p> <p>SKG-R4 Prod deployment of PUMA at SOLEIL facility Update PUMA versions at ESRF and ILL PaNOSC facilities.</p> <p>FAIR-R6 Finalize and run a full benchmark for ESRF datasets.</p>
Month	Description				
32	<p>SKG-R1 Implement SKG-IF API on PUMA (ESRF internal SKG) to expose dataset/publication citation links in common format Implement SKG-IF API on ESRF Data Portal to expose datasets in common format</p> <p>SKG-R4 In ESRF Data Portal. improve dataset metadata. add dataset/publication citation links. (source used PUMA SKG-IF API)</p> <p>SKG-R4 Prod deployment of PUMA at SOLEIL facility Update PUMA versions at ESRF and ILL PaNOSC facilities.</p> <p>FAIR-R6 Finalize and run a full benchmark for ESRF datasets.</p>				

3.7. SOCIB KG

Name	SOCIB SKG		
Category	SKG/Supporting Service and Platform		
Service URL	https://search.ws.socib.es/api/ (internal) https://search.ws.socib.es (internal)		
Version	N/A	TRL	9 ⁹
Copyright owner(s)	SOCIB	Contributors	SOCIB
License	Proprietary - All Rights Reserved		
Forms of availability	Gitlab repository (source code)		
Code repository URL	https://gitlab.priv.socib.es/data-center/socib_api_search		
Documentation URL	Not available		
Other repositories	Not available		
PID	Not available		
Software Quality Assurance measures	Static code analysis, accessibility compliance testing.		
Work performed	<p>The work performed to date addresses the following requirements: DMP-R1, DMP-R3, SKG.R3, IF-R1, IF-R3, IF-R5. They are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data model evaluation and re-design to comply with RDA standards. 		

⁹ For specific internal use

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SKG-IF core data model was implemented; to extend instrument representation - Storage re-design to facilitate assessments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ maDMPs are stored in the SKG; assessments dashboard to be implemented - Integration of DMP in SKG <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Import of maDMP and representation in the graph is in progress - Create maDMP templates <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ RDA DCS data model implemented; JSON export in progress - Harvesters' agent integration into DMP editor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Development in progress <p>JERCO-SKG and SOCIB SKG will be two instances of the same service: the former to serve the wider marine community and the latter for institutional purpose.</p>				
Milestones	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr style="background-color: #d3d3d3;"> <th style="width: 15%;">Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">32</td> <td>Align the SOCIB KG with OSTrails Commons. Implementation of SKG-IF API.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	Align the SOCIB KG with OSTrails Commons. Implementation of SKG-IF API.
Month	Description				
32	Align the SOCIB KG with OSTrails Commons. Implementation of SKG-IF API.				

3.8. SSH Open Marketplace (SSHOMP)

Name	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace (SSHOMP)		
Category	SKG		
Service URL	https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/		
Version	N/A	TRL	8
Copyright owner(s)	DARIAH/CLARIN/CES SDA	Contributors	DARIAH/CLARIN/CESSDA plus EB
License	Apache-2.0 license: https://github.com/SSHOC/sshoc-marketplace-frontend#Apache-2.0-1-ov-file		
Forms of availability	Service endpoint: https://marketplace-api.sshopencloud.eu/swagger-ui/index.html?url=/v3/api-docs App-marketplace: https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/		

Code repository URL	https://github.com/SSHOC/sshoc-marketplace-frontend and https://github.com/SSHOC/sshoc-marketplace-backend				
Documentation URL	https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/about/implementation https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/contribute/metadata-guidelines				
Other repositories	Not available				
PID	Does not apply as the SSHOMP is a repository itself. For entries, PIDs are recorded if available but SSHOMP does not issue PIDs.				
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>We have implemented the following quality assurance measures to ensure the reliability and security of our codebase:</p> <p>Testing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unit Tests: Ensuring individual components function as expected. Integration Tests: Verifying that different parts of the system work together seamlessly. Code Coverage: Metrics are available to illustrate the extent of test coverage <p>Security:</p> <p>While penetration testing and static code analysis have not yet been performed, we are open to collaborating with the security team to explore and execute these measures if needed.</p> <p>Code Quality:</p> <p>Current testing practices indirectly support code quality by identifying regressions and functional issues.</p>				
Work performed	- Analysis / evaluation of the SKG-IF API as basis for its implementation in the SSHOMP				
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Final version of SKG-based API, evaluated through use cases (Marketplace with new entities from other SKGs)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	Final version of SKG-based API, evaluated through use cases (Marketplace with new entities from other SKGs)
Month	Description				
32	Final version of SKG-based API, evaluated through use cases (Marketplace with new entities from other SKGs)				

3.9. Virtual Language Observatory (VLO)

Name	Virtual Language Observatory
------	------------------------------

Category	SKG						
Service URL	https://vlo.clarin.eu/						
Version	4.12.3	TRL	9				
Copyright owner(s)	CLARIN ERIC	Contributors	CLARIN centers				
License	GPL v3.0						
Forms of availability	Code repository , SSHOC open marketplace						
Code repository URL	https://github.com/clarin-eric/VLO						
Documentation URL	Users: https://vlo.clarin.eu/help Developers: https://github.com/clarin-eric/VLO/blob/master/README.md						
PID	https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.429b28						
Software Quality Assurance measures	Software analysis using Snyk: https://snyk.io/ Continuous Integration incl. automated tests. SauceLab for browser testing: https://saucelabs.com/						
Work performed	The basis for the SKG IF support by the VLO will be CMDI2RDF, which has been updated to deal with the latest version of CMDI, i.e., 1.2, and store its results in GraphDB. Work on implementing the SKG-IF on this basis has started.						
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Interaction with neighbouring SKG's</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	32	Interaction with neighbouring SKG's
Month	Description						
32	Interaction with neighbouring SKG's						

3.10. OPUS CTA Provenance

Name	OPUS (Observatoire de Paris UWS System)
------	---

Category	SKG		
Service URL	Test service at https://voparis-uws-test.obspm.fr/		
Version	V0.5	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	PADC (Paris Astronomical Data Centre)	Contributors	
License	MIT License		
Forms of availability	code repository / service endpoint		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/ParisAstronomicalDataCentre/OPUS		
Documentation URL	https://opus-job-manager.readthedocs.io https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2022ASPC..532..451S		
Other repositories			
PID	DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14833881		
Software Quality Assurance measures	Unit tests		
Work performed	<p>OPUS provides an interface to expose provenance graphs compatible with IVOA and W3C standards.</p> <p>We are preparing the connection to the SKG IF for the access to provenance information.</p> <p>The initial work was to locate what parts of the SKG-IF are relevant for OPUS. We particularly focus on the core entity "Research product", of type "research data", that OPUS generates. However, the OPUS system needs to get more information on the input data and processing steps, so that it will provide topics, contributions and manifestations for data products, attached to the provenance information already recorded.</p>		

Milestones	Month	Description
	32	SKG-IF interface integrated to OPUS

4. FAIR Assessment Platforms

4.1. CESSDA Metadata Validator (CMV)

Name	CESSDA Metadata Validator (CMV) - ID006		
Category	FAIR Assessment Platform		
Service URL	https://cmv.cessda.eu/#!validation		
Version	4.0.1 ¹⁰	TRL	8 ¹¹
Copyright owner(s)	CESSDA ERIC	Contributors	CESSDA and Service Providers
License	Software: Apache-2.0 https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0 Documentation and Profiles: CC-BY-4.0 https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/		
Forms of availability	Code repository, source code bundle, service endpoint, app marketplace		
Code repository URL	Application: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.console - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.core - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.server User Guide: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.documentation Metadata Profiles: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.metadata.profiles 		
Documentation URL	User Guide: https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/index.html API: https://api.tech.cessda.eu/ (select 'CESSDA Metadata Validator')		

¹⁰ Release 4 FEB 2025

¹¹ <https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/services/requirements.html>

<p>Other repositories</p>	<p>Zenodo:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5711086 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4680639 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681200 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4050123 <p>EOSC EU Node Marketplace:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/software?q=CESSDA%20Metadata%20Validator
<p>PID</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5711086 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4680639 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681200 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4050123
<p>Software Quality Assurance measures</p>	<p>The source code for CESSDA Service components is periodically evaluated against the CESSDA Software Maturity Levels (https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/sml/index.html). Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md <p>The Jenkins build breaks if the CESSDA Software Quality Gate is not achieved: https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/software/quality-gate.html</p> <p>The repositories are checked using the EOSC SQAaaS tool (https://sqaaas.eosc-synergy.eu/full-assessment) and README files badged accordingly. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/README.md - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.console/blob/main/README.md <p>Tooling</p> <p>Jenkins: https://jenkins.cessda.eu/ (includes Unit Tests, test coverage, Static Analysis)</p> <p>SonarQube: https://sonarqube.cessda.eu/projects (assesses Reliability, Security, Maintainability)</p> <p>JMeter: https://jmeter.apache.org/ (load testing)</p>

Work performed	Agreement has been reached on modifications needed to CESSDA's DDI-C and DDI-L profiles to incorporate RORs. Namely, add PIDs for the organisational creators (author, PI) and for the affiliation of the individual creators. The new versions of DDI-C and DDI-L profiles implemented.					
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Month</th> <th style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">32</td> <td>If necessary, updated versions of the DDI-C and DDI-L profiles</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Month	Description	32	If necessary, updated versions of the DDI-C and DDI-L profiles
Month	Description					
32	If necessary, updated versions of the DDI-C and DDI-L profiles					

4.2. FAIR-Aware

Name	FAIR-Aware		
Category	FAIR Knowledge Assessment tool		
Service URL	https://fairaware.dans.knaw.nl (English) https://doranum.fr/appli-fair-aware-pleine-page-vf/ (French)		
Version	1.0.1 (Current production version)	TRL	8
Copyright owner(s)	Version 1.0.1 ¹² Version 2.0: KNAW-DANS	Contributors	
License	MIT License		
Forms of availability	Code repository containing HTML, JavaScript and CSS plus images and documentation.		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/DANS-KNAW/fair-assessment-tool/tree/master		
Documentation URL	https://github.com/DANS-KNAW/fair-assessment-tool/tree/master/documents		

¹² From the homepage of FAIR-Aware v.1.0.1 and GitHub repository - © Copyright 2021 - FAIRsFAIR “Fostering FAIR Data Practices In Europe”

Other repositories	N/A						
PID	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5084664						
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>Not known if quality assurance measures were applied at development time of version 1.0 and unfortunately the original coder has retired. However, it does not pass any badges of Software Quality Assurance as a Service (SQAaaS) assessment, but does pass Code Accessibility, Licensing and Code metadata criteria.</p> <p>Version 1.0.1 does not meet web accessibility compliance WCAG 2.2, EEA and EN 301 549 - AccessibilityChecker.org</p>						
Work performed	<p>Guidance and glossary content extracted and converted into JSON files ready for import into any FAIR guidance system (e.g. Compliance Assessment Toolkit) (FAIR-R5)</p> <p>Further development of the specification for version 2.0 of FAIR-Aware undertaken to facilitate language independence, and the ability to create guidance and question sets for other digital object types. (IF-R2, IF-R4).</p> <p>FAIR-Aware v.1.0.1 has had its database upgraded; the Web interface now meets EU accessibility requirements and dead links will be fixed.</p>						
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>FAIR-Aware v.1.0.1 will continue to be available and supported for use both for training and self-directed study</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	32	FAIR-Aware v.1.0.1 will continue to be available and supported for use both for training and self-directed study
Month	Description						
32	FAIR-Aware v.1.0.1 will continue to be available and supported for use both for training and self-directed study						

4.3. FAIR Champion (ex FAIR Evaluator)

Name	FAIR Champion		
Category	FAIR Assessment		
Service URL	https://tools.ostrails.eu/champion		
Version	0.1	TRL	6/7 ¹³

¹³ TRL presented refers to current revision; previous FAIR Evaluator TRL is 9.

Copyright owner(s)	Mark D. Wilkinson	Contributors	
License	MIT		
Forms of availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Container - Code repository - Service endpoint. 		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/ OSTrails /FAIR-Champion		
Documentation URL	https://github.com/OSTrails/FAIR-Champion/		
Other repositories	N/A		
PID	N/A		
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>Creation of a test harness for Champion is complete. The Champion has two independent repositories– The Champion assessment platform, and the Champion (individual) Tests. A test harness for the individual tests (using RSpec) to ensure their compliance with the EOSC-recommended FAIR Signposting metadata harvesting is part of the Champion Tests repository and shows 100% pass.</p> <p>All platforms must be tested against the JSON Schema for FAIR Test Results to ensure that their outputs are harmonized. This is currently done semi-automatically, and as of this Deliverable, the Champion and FOOPS! Platforms are compliant.</p>		
Work performed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of Benchmarking and Benchmark Assessments - Creation of Benchmark template for easy reuse and authoring of novel benchmarks - Creation of the Guidance framework - Updates of all Tests to include the new Guidance elements in their output - Updates of Champion Benchmarking tool to include the new Guidance elements - Update of interface to allow re-analysis of test outputs from other platforms - Update of all interfaces for consistency and ease-of-use - Improvements in in-page documentation 		

	- Implementation of test harness, and automation via GitHub				
Milestones	<p>The emergence of the “Guidance Element” as part of the output of a test or benchmark now points to the need to visualize and explore these potentially complex “tutorials”, which will be embedded in the Champion output. Our objectives for the next 12 months are multi-fold, but related: 1) Capture community expectations in the form of Benchmarks and Algorithms, 2) Capture community-specific best practices in the form of Guidance Elements, 3) Link benchmarking outputs to guidance, 4) Improve the accessibility and interpretation of these Guidance Elements through dedicated exploration and visualization environments.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Full implementation of tools for community-specific guidance in Champion outputs</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	Full implementation of tools for community-specific guidance in Champion outputs
Month	Description				
32	Full implementation of tools for community-specific guidance in Champion outputs				

4.4. FAIR Assessment Authoring Tool

The FAIR Assessment Authoring Tool is a specialised module developed within the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) / FAIR Wizard ecosystem, enabling the structured creation of FAIR assessment components including benchmarks, metrics, and tests. While functionally integrated with DSW (see [Section 2.3](#)), it is presented as a separate entry in this deliverable to reflect the distinct contributions of UPM to its development within OSTrails. The tool leverages DSW's knowledge model infrastructure while providing dedicated functionality for FAIR assessment authoring.

Name	FAIR Assessment Authoring tool (DSW/FAIR Wizard module)		
Category	FAIR Assessment		
Service URL	https://ostrails-fair.fair-wizard.com/wizard/dashboard		
Version	1.0.0	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	Pablo Alarcon-Moreno	Contributors: Jakub Jirka Marek Suchánek	
License	CC0 (Creative Commons Zero)		

Forms of availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code repository - Service endpoint. 				
Code repository URL	https://registry.ds-wizard.org/knowledge-models/ostrails.eu:FAIR-assessment-authoring-tool:latest				
Documentation URL	https://github.com/OSTrails/docs/blob/commons-deliverable-m24/docs/commons/FAIR/FAIR-Assessment-Authoring-Tool.rst				
Other repositories	https://github.com/OSTrails/dsw-tdk-authoring-tool-template https://github.com/OSTrails/proxy-service-authoring-tool				
PID	N/A				
Software Quality Assurance measures	Regular updates and maintenance by the OSTrails team to ensure compliance with evolving guidelines.				
Work performed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capture metadata about the different FAIR assessment components (FAIR Benchmarks, Metrics, Tests, Benchmark Scoring Algorithms) in a machine-actionable way. - Template this information into a different serialization based on the expected metadata repository to author. - Metadata submission into different registries such as FAIRsharing, OSTrails GitHub Index and FAIR Data Point. 				
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Maintain compliance with FTR; Improve integration into GitHub and the FDP Index Proxy to simplify end-user experience</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	Maintain compliance with FTR; Improve integration into GitHub and the FDP Index Proxy to simplify end-user experience
Month	Description				
32	Maintain compliance with FTR; Improve integration into GitHub and the FDP Index Proxy to simplify end-user experience				

4.5. FAIR Validator

Name	FAIR Validator
Category	FAIR Assessment Service
Service URL	https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.metadata_validator/overview

Version	1.0.0	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	OpenAIRE ¹⁴	Contributors	OpenAIRE
License	Apache-2.0: https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0		
Forms of availability	Code repository + Service endpoint + Web application accessible online.		
Code repository URL	https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/uoa-validator-engine2 https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/uoa-validator-api https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/openaire-ostrails-api		
Documentation URL	TBD		
Other repositories	N/A		
PID	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17668519		
Software Quality Assurance measures	Regular updates and maintenance by the OpenAIRE team to ensure compliance with evolving guidelines.		
Work performed	<p>OpenAIRE has been working on adopting the FTR specification within the FAIR Metadata Validator. Our current efforts focus on developing an OSTrails-dedicated API that accepts FAIR validation requests for individual OAI-PMH record URLs. This API leverages the OpenAIRE Metadata Validator engine to evaluate each record and returns test results fully aligned with the FTR specification. We are now in the process of testing the compliance of this implementation by initiating tests and benchmarks to evaluate the integration into the Ostrails ecosystem.</p> <p>We will also provide Swagger documentation for the endpoints, along with user-friendly forms to support testing and integration.</p>		

¹⁴ OpenAIRE Service Catalogue:
https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.metadata_validator/overview

Milestones	Month	Description
	25	Prototype
	32	Fully compliant with the FTR specification and also the Guidance model.

4.6. FAIR Research Objects Assessment (FAIROS)

Name	FAIROS		
Category	FAIR Assessment		
Service URL	http://w3id.org/FAIROS/api		
Version	0.0.2	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	Esteban Gonzalez Daniel Garijo Alejandro Benitez	Contributors	Óscar Corcho
License	Apache 2.0 (https://github.com/oeg-upm/FAIR-Research-Object/blob/main/LICENSE)		
Forms of availability	Source code + Service endpoint		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/oeg-upm/FAIR-Research-Object		
Documentation URL	https://w3id.org/FAIROS		
Other repositories	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6599423		
PID	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6599423		

Software Quality Assurance measures	Implementation of a test to assess the results and the availability of the service. In addition, we have done an integration test with ROHub. Example: https://www.rohub.org/998dccd6-7192-4d88-af39-6018c71e6bdf				
Work performed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developed an API endpoint compliant with the FTR specification (v1.2.0). - Adapted F-UJI to the FTR specification to assess ROs and the datasets included in ROs - Worked towards including scoring algorithms from other assessment tools such as F-UJI (Datasets), FOOPS! (Ontologies) and RSFC (for software) - Adapted tool to work with the latest FOOPS! Version - Improved the integration with the ROHub platform - Documented tests, metrics and benchmarks used in FAIROs 				
Milestones	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr style="background-color: #d3d3d3;"> <th style="width: 15%;">Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">32</td> <td>Tests results performed to evaluate the integration of the tool into the OSTrails ecosystem. The results of the tests are published in SKGs, such as ROHub.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	Tests results performed to evaluate the integration of the tool into the OSTrails ecosystem. The results of the tests are published in SKGs, such as ROHub.
Month	Description				
32	Tests results performed to evaluate the integration of the tool into the OSTrails ecosystem. The results of the tests are published in SKGs, such as ROHub.				

4.7. Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR (FOOPS!)

Name	Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR (FOOPS!)		
Category	FAIR Assessment		
Service URL	https://w3id.org/foops		
Version	0.3.0	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	Daniel Garijo, María Poveda-Villalón	Contributors	Oscar Corcho
License	Apache 2.0 (https://github.com/oeg-upm/fair_ontologies/blob/main/LICENSE)		

Forms of availability	Code repository + Service endpoint	
Code repository URL	https://github.com/oeg-upm/fair_ontologies/	
Documentation URL	https://github.com/oeg-upm/fair_ontologies/blob/main/README.md	
Other repositories	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14768000 Catalogue of tests and metrics: https://w3id.org/foops/catalogue	
PID	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14768000	
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>FOOPS is a reference implementation of the FAIR-IF and the FTR specification.</p> <p>Test definitions and metrics have passed a SHACL shape validation test to comply with the FAIR-IF test specification.</p> <p>FOOPS! Has a battery of tests to assess its performance when new issues are fixed.</p>	
Work performed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of Benchmarking and Benchmark Assessments - Documentation of tests and metrics according to the latest FTR specification - Creation of reference benchmarks for ontology assessment - Updates of all Tests to include new guidance in the produced output - Improvements in in-page documentation - Implementation of the tool as an action - Registration of the FAIR metrics in FAIRSharing 	
Milestones	Month	Description
	32	FOOPS! Fully conforms with the FTR specification and API, including guidance elements in the test results. FOOPS! Is adopted by an orchestrating tool. Results produced by FOOPS! Are registered in an SKG.

4.8. IVOA Services Validation

Name	IVOA service Validation										
Category	FAIR Assessment										
Service URL	https://voparis-validation-reports.obspm.fr/api/										
Version	1.10	TRL	9								
Copyright owner(s)	ObsParis	Contributors	CNRS								
License	TBD.										
Forms of availability	Service endpoint										
Code repository URL	N/A										
Documentation URL	https://voparis-validation-reports.obspm.fr/										
Other repositories	N/A										
PID	N/A										
Software Quality Assurance measures	TBD										
Work performed	First set of FAIR metrics has been prepared and discussed with the IVOA group .										
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>First draft of tests and metrics</td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td>First prototype</td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Effective assessment of ESCAPE Pilot resources</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	18	First draft of tests and metrics	24	First prototype	32	Effective assessment of ESCAPE Pilot resources
Month	Description										
18	First draft of tests and metrics										
24	First prototype										
32	Effective assessment of ESCAPE Pilot resources										

4.9. PADC Validator

Name	PADC Validator Service						
Category	FAIR Assessment						
Service URL	http://voparis-validator.obspm.fr/						
Version	TBD	TRL	9				
Copyright owner(s)	ObsParis	Contributors	CNRS				
License	TBD						
Forms of availability	service endpoint						
Code repository URL	TBD						
Documentation URL	TBD						
Other repositories	N/A						
PID	TBD						
Software Quality Assurance measures	TBD						
Work performed	Preparing FAIR-Assessment metrics including PADC Validator results						
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td>First draft of tests and metrics</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	18	First draft of tests and metrics
Month	Description						
18	First draft of tests and metrics						

	24	First prototype
	32	Effective assessment of ESCAPE Pilot resources

5. Other Supporting Services and Platforms

5.1. CESSDA ELSST

Name	CESSDA European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) - ID003		
Category	Supporting Services and Platforms		
Service URL	https://thesauri.cessda.eu/elsst-6/en/		
Version	6.0	TRL	8
Copyright owner(s)	CESSDA ERIC (content, not code)	Contributors	CESSDA and Service Providers
License	Documentation: CC-BY-4.0 https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/		
Forms of availability	Service endpoint, app marketplace		
Code repository URL	N/A (uses 3 rd party application to publish curated content)		
Documentation URL	User Guide: https://elsst.cessda.eu/ API: https://api.tech.cessda.eu/ (select 'CESSDA ELSST Thesaurus')		
Other repositories	Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4063933 EOSC EU Node Marketplace: https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/data/50%257Cdoi_dedup_%253A%253Aa5095d6e7764ec39d2d9f5b448611c52 SSH Open Marketplace: https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/fljrOK		

PID	10.5281/zenodo.4063933						
Software Quality Assurance measures	N/A						
Work performed	Implemented first version of SKG-IF which retrieve ELSST topics by ID (escaped/unescaped URIs) and enables search for topics with filters (e.g., by label or language). Provided feedback on SKG-IF API specification.						
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.
Month	Description						
32	Test use cases against the newly built SKG federation.						

5.2. CESSDA Vocabulary Service

Name	CESSDA Vocabulary Service (CVS) - ID008		
Category	Supporting Services and Platforms		
Service URL	https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/		
Version	3.5.2	TRL	8 ¹⁵
Copyright owner(s)	CESSDA ERIC	Contributors	CESSDA and Service Providers
License	Software: Apache-2.0 https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0 Documentation: CC-BY-4.0 https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/		
Forms of availability	Code repository, source code bundle, service endpoint, app marketplace		

¹⁵ <https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/services/requirements.html>

Code repository URL	<p>Application: https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cvs.two</p> <p>User Guide: https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cvs.userguide</p> <p>Content Editors' Guide: https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cvs.contentguide</p>
Documentation URL	<p>User Guide: https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/documentation/</p> <p>Content Editors' Guide: Only available to authenticated users</p> <p>API: https://api.tech.cessda.eu/ (select 'CESSDA Vocabulary Service')</p>
Other repositories	<p>Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6092398</p> <p>EOSC EU Node Marketplace: https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/software/50%257Cdoi_dedup_%253A%253A394aacec99e0d7fb2ec782930d4cc739</p>
PID	10.5281/zenodo.6092398
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>The source code for CESSDA Service components is periodically evaluated against the CESSDA Software Maturity Levels (https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/sml/index.html)</p> <p>Examples: https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md</p> <p>The Jenkins build breaks if the CESSDA Software Quality Gate is not achieved: https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/software/quality-gate.html</p> <p>The repositories are checked using the EOSC SQAaaS tool (https://sqaaas.eosc-synergy.eu/full-assessment) and the README files are badged accordingly. Examples:</p> <p>https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/README.md</p> <p>https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.console/blob/main/README.md</p> <p>Tooling</p>

	Jenkins: https://jenkins.cessda.eu/ (includes Unit Tests, test coverage, Static Analysis) SonarQube: https://sonarqube.cessda.eu/projects (assesses Reliability, Security, Maintainability) JMeter: https://jmeter.apache.org/ (load testing)					
Work Performed	None					
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td> Define Use Cases. First implementation of SKG-IF based API. Test use cases against the SKG-IF API. SKG-IF specification - provide feedback and contributions. </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Month	Description	32	Define Use Cases. First implementation of SKG-IF based API. Test use cases against the SKG-IF API. SKG-IF specification - provide feedback and contributions.
Month	Description					
32	Define Use Cases. First implementation of SKG-IF based API. Test use cases against the SKG-IF API. SKG-IF specification - provide feedback and contributions.					

5.3. CESSDA Metadata Aggregator

Name	CESSDA Metadata Aggregator - ID048		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai		
Version	0.10.0 ¹⁶	TRL	8 ¹⁷
Copyright owner(s)	CESSDA ERIC	Contributors	CESSDA and Service Providers
License	Software: EUPL-1.2 Documentation: CC-BY-4.0 https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/		
Forms of availability	Code repository, source code bundle, service endpoint		

¹⁶ Release 17 JAN 2025

¹⁷ See: <https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/services/requirements.html>

Code repository URL	<p>OAI-PMH endpoint (SKG API):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.doc-store.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.client.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.oai-pmh-repo-handler.git - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.aggregator.devguide.git
Documentation URL	<p>OAI-PMH API: https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=Identify</p> <p>OAI-PMH Developer's guide: https://cessda-metadata-aggregator.readthedocs.io/en/stable/</p>
Other repositories	<p>Zenodo (OAI-PMH endpoint):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779957 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779936 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779782 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779897
PID	<p>OAI-PMH endpoint:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779957 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779936 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779782 - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779897
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>The source code for CESSDA Service components is periodically evaluated against the CESSDA Software Maturity Levels (https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/sml/index.html). Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/SML.md <p>The Jenkins build fails if the CESSDA Software Quality Gate is not achieved (https://docs.tech.cessda.eu/software/quality-gate.html)</p> <p>The repositories are checked using the EOSC SQAaaS tool (https://sqaas.eosc-synergy.eu/full-assessment) and README files badged accordingly. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cdc.osmh-indexer.cmm/blob/main/README.md - https://github.com/cessda/cessda.cmv.console/blob/main/README.md <p>Tooling</p>

	<p>Jenkins: https://jenkins.cessda.eu/ (includes Unit Tests, test coverage, Static Analysis)</p> <p>SonarQube: https://sonarqube.cessda.eu/projects (assesses Reliability, Security, Maintainability)</p> <p>JMeter: https://jmeter.apache.org/ (load testing)</p>				
Work performed	<p>Agreement has been reached on modifications needed to CESSDA's DDI-C and DDI-L profiles to incorporate RORs. Namely, add PIDs for the organizational creators (author, PI) and for the affiliation of the individual creators.</p> <p>Modifications adopted by some Publishers to enrich their metadata, which is now in the CESSDA Data Catalogue.</p> <p>The initial version of the SKG-IF for the CESSDA Data Catalogue has been released. Provided feedback on SKG-IF API specification.</p>				
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Test CDC use cases against the newly built SKG federation.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	Test CDC use cases against the newly built SKG federation.
Month	Description				
32	Test CDC use cases against the newly built SKG federation.				

5.4. FAIRassist

Name	FAIRassist		
Category	Supporting Service		
Service URL	https://fairassist.org/registry		
Version	Beta	TRL	6
Copyright owner(s)	University of Oxford	Contributors	University of Oxford
License	Content: CC-BY-SA-4.0, https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/legalcode		
Forms of availability	Service endpoint, data catalogue		

Code repository URL	Web application (from FAIRsharing): https://github.com/FAIRsharing/fairsharing.github.io/				
Documentation URL	(in progress, and part of FAIRsharing) https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/associated-records/from-fairassist-records https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/record-sections-and-fields/general-information/registry-type#fairassist				
Other repositories					
PID	(to be minted)				
Software Quality Assurance measures	CI unit testing, code coverage measurement, njsscan, codacy scanning, brakeman testing on API, API integration testing.				
Work performed	Contributed to the definition of the FAIR assessment IF of Dimensions, Metrics, Benchmarks and Test. Designed and implemented this new FAIRassist registry, as a component of FAIRsharing to assist with the assessment. This new registry will describe FAIR Principles (or Dimensions), related Metrics and Benchmarks (that will be related to relevant standards, in the main FAIRsharing registry), the latter two cross-referenced to the Tests.				
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Implemented and launched a beta version; started to registered Dimensions, Metrics, Benchmarks.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	Implemented and launched a beta version; started to registered Dimensions, Metrics, Benchmarks.
Month	Description				
32	Implemented and launched a beta version; started to registered Dimensions, Metrics, Benchmarks.				

5.5. Lenticular Lens

Name	Lenticular Lens		
Category	Supporting Service		
Service URL	https://lenticularlens.org/		
Version	1.23	TRL	9

Copyright owner(s)	KNAW HuC	Contributors	KNAW HuC				
License	MIT						
Forms of availability	code repository https://lenticularlens.goldenagents.org						
Code repository URL	https://github.com/knaw-huc/lenticular-lens						
Documentation URL	https://lenticularlens.org/						
Other repositories	https://github.com/knaw-huc/lenticular-lens-org https://github.com/knaw-huc/lenticular-lens-gui-react https://github.com/knaw-huc/lenticular-lens-postgresql						
PID	hdl:1148d8d1-a16d-4cf9-a5b9-07dedc027502						
Software Quality Assurance measures	Software analysis using Snyk: https://snyk.io/						
Work performed	LL can interact with a SPARQL endpoint and use the JSON-LD terminology, i.e. the names used by a JSON-LD context. To fully test this for an SKG access to a functional endpoint is required.						
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Support alignment of entities between OSTrails SKGs</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	32	Support alignment of entities between OSTrails SKGs
Month	Description						
32	Support alignment of entities between OSTrails SKGs						

5.6. OpenAIRE Broker

Name	OpenAIRE Broker
Category	Supporting Service or Platform

Service URL	https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.broker/overview		
Version	OpenAIRE Content Provider Dashboard integration v3.8.0 Public API v3.8.0	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	OpenAIRE	Contributors	OpenAIRE, CNR
License	Software: GPL-3.0-or-later https://spdx.org/licenses/GPL-3.0-or-later.html		
Forms of availability	Accessible via the OpenAIRE Content Provider Dashboard and through APIs.		
Code repository URL	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-applications/src/branch/master/apps/dhp-broker-application https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop/src/branch/main/dhp-workflows/dhp-broker-events https://github.com/openaire/broker-cmdline-client ¹⁸		
Documentation URL	https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/apis/broker-api/		
Other repositories	https://central.sonatype.com/artifact/eu.openaire/broker-client		
PID	N/A		
Software Quality Assurance measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CI/CD infrastructure to ensure repeatable, trusted delivery. - Static Code Analysis using SonarQube software. - Unit tests 		

¹⁸ 026_OpenAIRE-Broker.pptx:

https://openaireeu.sharepoint.com/:p:/s/OSTrails/EYvRDnO_CMIAgporO0LXNq0BqE2BRC8sVztXkCdq_2RzgA?e=Gyrhna

Work performed	<p>Added Value Analysis of OpenAIRE Graph Contents</p> <p>The analysis showed limited potential for creating new subscription topics related to links between publications and peer reviews or publications and DMPs, contrary to the original plan. However, it confirmed the presence of links between publications and datasets, as well as publications and software—connections not widely recognised in many repositories. This finding provides a strong foundation for designing new subscription topics in the Broker service, aimed at enriching linkages to additional digital objects.</p> <p>Continuous Validation Mechanism</p> <p>A continuous validation process was introduced in the production environment of the OpenAIRE metadata aggregation system. This mechanism checks input records against the OpenAIRE Guidelines. The resulting validation reports form the basis for “metadata alerts”, which provide quality indicators for metadata in OpenAIRE Provide via the Broker service.</p>								
Milestones	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr style="background-color: #d3d3d3;"> <th style="width: 15%;">Month</th> <th colspan="2">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">32</td> <td colspan="2">Production release</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description		32	Production release	
Month	Description								
32	Production release								

5.7. OpenOrgs

Name	OpenOrgs		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	Service: https://orgs.openaire.eu Portal: https://openorgs.openaire.eu		
Version	3.7.2	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	OpenAIRE	Contributors	OpenAIRE, CNR, RBI
License	Software: GPL-3.0-or-later https://spdx.org/licenses/GPL-3.0-or-later.html		
Forms of availability	Via the public portal - https://openorgs.openaire.eu Via the data curation tool - https://orgs.openaire.eu		

	<p>Via the OpenAIRE Graph API - https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/apis/graph-api/</p> <p>Via the data snapshot - https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13271358</p>
Code repository URL	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-applications/src/branch/master/apps/dnet-orgs-database-application
Documentation URL	https://openorgs.openaire.eu/what-is-openorgs https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/data-model/entities/organization
Other repositories	https://maven.d4science.org/nexus/service/local/repositories/dnet45-snapshots/content/eu/dnetlib/dhp/dnet-orgs-database-application/maven-metadata.xml
PID	N/A
Software Quality Assurance measures	<p>Regular updates and the integration of community feedback to ensure reliability and continuous improvement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CI/CD infrastructure to ensure repeatable, trusted delivery. - Static Code Analysis using SonarQube software. - Unit tests
Work performed	<p>The work carried out from M14 to M24 addressed these main tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The planned pilot activity with Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (vu.nl) was successfully completed. It focused on retrieving complete and authoritative information about Dutch organisation (sub)units from CRIS system. After curation through OpenOrgs and integration with affiliation data, this has significantly improved the accuracy and coverage of the Netherlands monitor. The approach serves as a model for similar national integrations where comparable structured data is available. - To support the processing of hierarchical information from VU Amsterdam and similar sources, a new workflow has been implemented in OpenOrgs. It enables curators to efficiently identify, add, and validate parent-child relationships between organisational units, improving consistency in hierarchy modelling and strengthening the overall quality and interoperability of organisation records in the OpenAIRE Graph. - Further work is ongoing on the OpenAIRE Graph API that returns organisation records, with the aim of introducing a response format that fully conforms to the SKG-IF specification.

Milestones	Month	Description
	32	Extension of the API response format in line with the SKG-IF specification and production release of the SKG-IF compliant Graph API response format.

5.8. ROHub

Name	ROHub		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://www.rohub.org/		
Version	Portal v4.1.0 Service 2.1.81	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	PSNC	Contributors	
License	ROHub portal and service: Closed ROHub Python library MIT		
Forms of availability	ROHub portal available via portal endpoint, possible also binary for on-site deployments ROHub service available via service endpoint, possible also binary for on-site deployments Python library in code repository, pip package		
Code repository URL	Service: https://gitlab.pcss.pl/rohub/rohub-backend/rohub2020 (private) Portal: https://gitlab.pcss.pl/rohub/rohub-frontend/rohub2020-frontend (private) Python library: https://gitlab.pcss.pl/daisd-public/rohub/rohub-api (public)		
Documentation URL	https://reliance-eosc.github.io/rohub-portal-documentation/ Tutorial: https://reliance-eosc.github.io/ROHUB-API_documentation/html/tutorials.html		

	<p>API: https://reliance-eosc.github.io/ROHUB-API_documentation/html/modules.html</p> <p>API Jupyter Notebook demo: https://github.com/RELIANCE-EOSC/sample-notebooks</p>
Other repositories	N/A
PID	<p>https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.d3c5fd</p> <p>https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013832</p>
Software Quality Assurance measures	Unit testing, integrated unit testing, continuous integration, sentry, nagios
Work performed	<p>Initial implementation of OSTrails SKG-IF to expose RO-Crates as Scientific Knowledge Graphs. This required the specification and implementation of the mapping of the RO-Crate metadata to the SKG-IF data model. This will allow the integration and/or harvesting of RO-Crate metadata in other SKGs that will use this API to harvest metadata, like OpenAire that plans to use such API in the future for harvesting. Currently, OpenAire SKG harvest metadata about RO-Crates (and other key resources) from ROHub via its OAI-PMH endpoint.</p> <p>ROHub also updated the serialization of RO-Crates based on the latest community specification (v1.2) , and updated/improved the communication with various OSTrails related tools and services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regarding FAIR assessments tools, ROHub integrates FAIROS, which assesses the FAIRness of RO-Crates (and aggregated resources). After the implementation of the latest RO-Crate specification in ROHub, FAIROS is being updated to support the traversing of the RO-Crate structure. - Regarding DMPs, ROHub currently supports importing DMPs from ARGOS (in XML), which generate RO-Crates for the management of ma-DMPs. This required the specification and implementation of a mapping between the DMP questions to machine-actionable metadata in the RO-Crate. This metadata was based on the RDA DCS model. Currently, we are updating ROHub to support ma-DMPs directly from the tools, like ARGOS. This requires updating the functionality to import DMP as well as updating the connection from ARGOS to ROHub in the Polish instance of ARGOS.

	<p>ROHub exposes OpenAPI specifications and REST architectural styles (IF-R8), and the representation and exchange of data in semantically rich formats like RDF to enhance interoperability (IF-R10), particularly using RO-crate specification for data exchange (IF-R1), which is based on JSON-LD data format (IF-R3), the use of PIDs for referencing data and contextual entities (IF-R5), and on using common published vocabularies, chiefly schema.org (IF-R7). Additionally, initial work has been taken to facilitate integration of institutional repositories of research data and publications (IF-R11) in ROHub.</p>						
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Month</th> <th style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">32</td> <td>Implementation and use of OStrails IF for communication with FAIROs (if compliant), OpenAire SKG (if compliant) and ARGOS (if compliant)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	32	Implementation and use of OStrails IF for communication with FAIROs (if compliant), OpenAire SKG (if compliant) and ARGOS (if compliant)
Month	Description						
32	Implementation and use of OStrails IF for communication with FAIROs (if compliant), OpenAire SKG (if compliant) and ARGOS (if compliant)						

5.9. SOMEF

Name	Software Metadata Extraction Framework (SoMEF)		
Category	Supporting Service		
Service URL	https://somef.linkeddata.es/#/		
Version	0.9.12	TRL	7
Copyright owner(s)	Daniel Garijo	Contributors	
License	MIT License https://github.com/KnowledgeCaptureAndDiscovery/somef/blob/master/LICENSE		
Forms of availability	Container + Source code		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/KnowledgeCaptureAndDiscovery/somef/		
Documentation URL	https://somef.readthedocs.io/en/latest/		

Other repositories	N/A				
PID	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14780377 https://archive.softwareheritage.org/swh:1:dir:118b192ae433383ff1f60512d3869b24b0648393;origin=https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3477929;visit=swh:1:snp:64a22f7c09abdf2b834d6bcbe1f852ceab9da699;anchor=swh:1:rel:0ae2f5e55132f9a3bb6aedc1a74c1fc603e78474;path=KnowledgeCaptureAndDiscovery-somef-a33c984				
Software Quality Assurance measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Battery of tests implemented - GitHub actions are enabled for releases of packages - Poetry environment is used for reproducibility 				
Work performed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extension of SOMEF to recognize additional metadata formats used in source code repositories in different programming languages. - Incorporation of SOMEF in the RSFC tool (used in FAIROs) for FAIR assessment of research software, based on the requirements described in the RSMD guidelines (https://fair-impact.github.io/RSMD-guidelines/) - Alignment of SOMEF against community standards for Research Software metadata such as CodeMeta. 				
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>SOMEF is consumed by FAIR assessment tools and SKGs to extract key metadata needed for running test results</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	SOMEF is consumed by FAIR assessment tools and SKGs to extract key metadata needed for running test results
Month	Description				
32	SOMEF is consumed by FAIR assessment tools and SKGs to extract key metadata needed for running test results				

5.10. SSH Data Citation Service

Name	SSH Data Citation Service (DCS)		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html		
Version	0.7	TRL	8

Copyright owner(s)	Institute of Information Science and Technologies "Alessandro Faedo" - (ISTI) - CNR	Contributors	ISTI – CNR, ILC - CNR				
License	Software: Apache-2.0 https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0						
Forms of availability	Source code available, public REST API, demo Web UI						
Code repository URL	https://gitea-s2i2s.isti.cnr.it/concordia/sshoc-citationservice						
Documentation URL	<p>Technical documentation is being created, Swagger documentation for REST API is available here:</p> <p>https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citationservice/swagger-ui.html</p> <p>A document describing motivations and design assumptions of the DCS:</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3595965</p> <p>A paper describing the DCS:</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-16802-4_32</p>						
Other repositories	N/A						
PID	N/A						
Software Quality Assurance measures	The development environment is being finalized, it includes state of art frameworks to implement code analysis and testing						
Work performed	DCS will use the SKG IF, therefore work is in progress to update APIs to act as integration layer implementing the SKG IF model. Activity is being carried on improving the Authentication Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) module of the DCS to implement OAuth 2.0, (see IF-R4)						
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description		
Month	Description						

5.11. SSH Vocabulary Commons

Name	Social Sciences & Humanities Vocabulary Commons		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse		
Version	N/A (currently based on Skosmos 2.16)	TRL	8
Copyright owner(s)	N/A	Contributors	ACDH (ÖAW), CLARIN, SSHOC
License	MIT for the underlying software (Skosmos): https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/vocabs-update-theme/blob/main/LICENSE		
Forms of availability	Code repository: https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/vocabs-common Vocabulary dumps: https://github.com/SSHOC/vocabularies Container: https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/vocabs-common/pkgs/container/vocabs-common API endpoint: Swagger UI		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/vocabs-common		
Documentation URL	https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/eN/About For underlying software (Skosmos): https://github.com/NatLibFi/Skosmos/wiki For API (Skosmos): http://api.finto.fi/doc/#/		
Other repositories	Not available		

PID	N/A						
Software Quality Assurance measures	Responsibility of the developers of the Skosmos software (National Library Finland).						
Work performed	- Study of role of vocabulary services in relation to SKGs						
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td> Study and planning for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitating shared editorial responsibility - Expanding federated vocabulary (metadata) search Exploring relation of Vocabulary Service to FAIRsharing Implementation of the SKG-IF topic-endpoint for vocabularies in hosted by Vocab Commons </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Month	Description	32	Study and planning for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitating shared editorial responsibility - Expanding federated vocabulary (metadata) search Exploring relation of Vocabulary Service to FAIRsharing Implementation of the SKG-IF topic-endpoint for vocabularies in hosted by Vocab Commons
Month	Description						
32	Study and planning for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitating shared editorial responsibility - Expanding federated vocabulary (metadata) search Exploring relation of Vocabulary Service to FAIRsharing Implementation of the SKG-IF topic-endpoint for vocabularies in hosted by Vocab Commons						

5.12. DataRepositóriUM

Name	DataRepositóriUM		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://datarepositorium.uminho.pt/		
Version	Dataverse 4.20	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	DataRepositóriUM: University of Minho Dataverse software: Institute for Quantitative Social Science, Harvard University	Contributors	Dataverse software: Global Dataverse Community Consortium

License	The Dataverse software is licensed under the Apache License Version 2.0. https://github.com/IQSS/dataverse/blob/develop/LICENSE.md				
Forms of availability	Via the public portal: https://datarepositorium.uminho.pt/ Via the repository OAI-PMH interface: https://datarepositorium.uminho.pt/oai?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oai_dc Via the API (Dataverse): https://guides.dataverse.org/en/4.20/api/intro.html#lists-of-dataverse-apis				
Code repository URL	https://github.com/IQSS/dataverse				
Documentation URL	https://guides.dataverse.org/en/4.20/developers/index.html https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/admin/index.html				
Other repositories	Docker Container Guide: https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/container/index.html Dataverse roadmap: https://www.iq.harvard.edu/roadmap-dataverse-project				
PID	N/A				
Software Quality Assurance measures	Quality Assurance measures described at https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/qa/overview.html				
Work performed	None				
Milestones	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>32</td> <td>Integration with ARGOS API and FAIR assessment / validation tools, in line with the Portuguese National Pilot.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	32	Integration with ARGOS API and FAIR assessment / validation tools, in line with the Portuguese National Pilot.
Month	Description				
32	Integration with ARGOS API and FAIR assessment / validation tools, in line with the Portuguese National Pilot.				

5.13. RCAAP

Name	RCAAP Portuguese Open Access Scientific Repositories		
Category	Supporting Service or Platform		
Service URL	https://www.rcaap.pt/		
Version	N/A	TRL	9
Copyright owner(s)	FCT-FCCN (front-end); La referencia (back-end)	Contributors	University of Minho
License	Front-end NA; Back-end AJPL3.0		
Forms of availability	Via the public portal: https://www.rcaap.pt/ Via the repository OAI-PMH interface: https://www.rcaap.pt/oai/openaire4?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oai_openaire		
Code repository URL	https://github.com/lareferencia/lareferencia-lrharvester-app		
Documentation URL	https://projeto.rcaap.pt/		
Other repositories	https://www.rcaap.pt/directory.jsp https://www.indexar.pt		
PID	NA		
Software Quality Assurance measures	NA		
Work performed	None		

Milestones

None set presently. To be placed in next period of the project.

Month	Description
32	Integration with ARGOS API and FAIR assessment / validation tools.

6. Conclusions – Next Steps

This report continues supporting the findings of its previous version ([D2.2](#)), confirming that a very large subset of tools introduced in [D2.1](#) evolved in the context of OSTrails WP2 in the directions set by its vision and fulfilling the requirements that were identified and prioritized early in the project. Moreover, new subproducts have emerged as result of the work performed during the last period of the project.

As an overview of the major changes over the previous version of the deliverable are as follows:

- FAIRassist has been separated from FAIRsharing to serve as registry of FAIR dimensions, metrics and benchmarks.
- The FAIR Assessment Authoring Tool, developed as an extension to the DSW, is listed separately to reflect the distinct partner contributions while remaining functionally integrated within the DSW ecosystem.
- [TUWRD \(TU Wien Research Data\)](#) has been removed from the list of software to be evolving in the context of OSTrail, as the connection with the DMP platform [DAMAP](#) will be tackled by the later.
- Four (4) services, [IVOA Services Validation](#), [PADC Validator](#), [DataRepositóriUM](#) and [RCAAP](#) will begin their OSTrails alignment in the final project period, with targeted integrations planned for the M32 release.

A brief analysis of the results is that:

- 35 services as the total number of platforms evolving under OSTrails WP2.
- 31 of the services have already evolved in this period, the other preparing for next step of implementation.
- The vast majority of the software is Open Source under common FOSS licenses, and many of the services presented are easily accessible.
- All of the currently listed platforms have an active evolution plan for the final period of OSTrails, with specific expectations and targets.

Looking ahead to M32, the final release will focus on consolidating cross-platform interoperability, expanding machine-actionable DMP support across additional community profiles, and strengthening the feedback loop between FAIR assessment outputs and DMP guidance. These developments will enable demonstration of complete Plan-Track-Assess workflows in operational pilot environments.

Figure 1: Overview of tool status

Figure 2: Tools implementing refinements in OSTrails WP2, per category

Figure 3: Tools reporting refinements to date in D2.3

Several tools have released interim versions or iterations prior to this general release, for example with the aim to validate integration as early as possible or to provide early support for pilots. This trend is expected to continue in addition to the last official releases, to be reported in the next and final version of this report.

7. References

1. Suchánek, M., Martínková, J., Wilkinson, M., Garijo, D., Miksa, T., Manghi, P., Dyume, R., Rey Mazón, M., Moilanen, K., Heinonen, M., Broeder, D., Spichtinger, D., Windhouwer, M., Príncipe, P., Vodopijevec, A., Macan, B., Steinhoff, W., Priddy, M., & Kontopidi, M. (2024). D2.1: Analysis of the OSTrails Interoperability Framework Tools Compliance. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880235>

Annex I – Description Template

The following template has been utilised in order to achieve a homogenously presentation of the work and outcomes for each platform.

Software/Service XYX

Name	Present the formal name of the service, platform, tool		
Category	<i>Choose one of: DMP/SKG/FAIR Assessment/Supporting Service or Platform</i>		
Service URL	<i>Place service URL, if applicable</i>		
Version	<i>If a versioning number is present and relevant, it should be placed here</i>	TRL	<i>Present the TRL of the item as of this release</i>
Copyright owner(s)	<i>Name the copyright owners (no need for details)</i>	Contributors	<i>If more contributors exist besides the copyright owners present those here.</i>
License	<i>Present the license name and its URL for reference.</i>		
Forms of availability	<i>Pick any or multiple of: Binary / container / code repository / source code bundle / service endpoint / app-marketplace ... (if various elements are provided in different forms, clarify which element is provided in each form).</i>		
Code repository URL	<i>Place repository URL (GitHub etc.). If FOSS, the repo should be accessible. If private, the link may be skipped, however still some evidence should be here for reference.</i>		
Documentation URL	<i>Present a (public) documentation URL</i>		
Other repositories	<i>Point out any other repositories related to software access in its various forms (e.g. docker hub, maven, Zenodo, community repositories etc.) along with URLs of the software.</i>		
PID	<i>PID for the software (good practice to have one, however if not available save for next iteration of the deliverable).</i>		

<p>Software Quality Assurance measures</p>	<p><i>Enumerate briefly the quality assurance measures taken. Security, code quality, testing measures should be presented. For instance: Static code analysis, penetration testing, accessibility compliance testing etc. If details for the processes are needed place those in the document below this card.</i></p>								
<p>Work performed</p>	<p><i>Present briefly the work performed up to M14. This is the most essential part of this document. Present here only work that is performed in OSTrails and in alignment with its objectives!</i></p> <p><i>Identify which of the requirements or directives presented Chapter 2 are being addressed during this period.</i></p> <p><i>Explicitly present work towards the alignment to draft architectural interoperability directives of OSTrails as known up to M12.</i></p>								
<p>Milestones</p>	<p><i>Enumerate major milestones of your future work in OSTrails referring to project months estimation ensuring alignment with the two updates of D2.2 at M24 and M32. (interim milestones may be present for some software depending on pilots and other dependencies, so add those at will). Adding an MTR milestone (M18) can also be helpful.</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="472 1048 1393 1209"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>24</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>32</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Description	18		24		32	
Month	Description								
18									
24									
32									